

Implementing AI-Driven tools in Project Management: Automating OYO regional project delivery processes.

Toriola Samuel Rotimi

Delivery Project Management - A non vendor specific solution to Regional Project Delivery

Abstract

This article examines the design, development and use case of an AI-driven bot in regional project delivery processes, and further explores the effect of implementation in optimizing workflow processes in a business environment. There are numerous ways to utilize AI in project management for basic work needs. AI-driven tools provide an avenue to automate repetitive tasks, allowing Project Managers to focus on other strategic aspects of management. To mention a few use cases further elaborated below include automating task scheduling and delegation, decision support systems, resource skill matching and shift planning, project forecasting and estimation, optimizing workloads by reducing activity duration, increasing productivity and eradicating the likelihood of human errors.

Introduction

To Implement AI in regional project delivery processes requires the introduction and adoption in the most natural way available. Leveraging domain-specific software is an option that can be used both internally within an organization or externally with customers, vendors and other stakeholders. The potential scalability to use in an enterprise solution, serving as a viable system to foster business intelligence by the provision of data-driven insights for decision-making on requirements timelines, resource availability, and the historical performance of key deliverable would be vital in tackling complex business challenges.

In an attempt to do more, we can engage with team members using social communications platforms in this case third-party messaging applications which are natural in terms of use in our day-to-day interaction and activities, requiring zero skills or training, enhancing team collaboration and further information transfer. We can leverage such a model to address gaps that may arrive in situations where cross-cultural communication is necessary in which verbal communication might not be the most efficient.

During communication in projects, from a sender to a receiver either in a one-to-one or one-to-many relationship, an assurance that information sent is interpreted correctly would require a more comprehensive approach. An interactive communication model is best with a high guarantee of information delivery and prompt feedback. Factors that may negatively influence efficient communication, specifically in the use of emails revolves mostly around the receiver's perception of the message, Improper addressing, lack of interest, lack of urgency, error decoding the message, losing mails and mail trials within broadcasts and change of subjects, several distractions to mention a few.

However, while we can utilize verbal skills such as repetition of key points, asking for feedback using questions, over simplification and

physical demonstration of intended action can be effective but are not applicable in all scenarios. For example, during senior management meetings misinterpretation of physical demonstration.

This significantly has a positive effect on project progress tracking, The open rate of text messages is 98% compared to the open rate of email at 20%, showcasing how highly effective this solution can be with numerous applications. This software solution simply relays scheduled activities from planner to assigned resource and receive feedback in real time to a spreadsheet from third party messaging applications like (Whats App & Telegram).

from unbiased collation and tracking information on planned site activities by shortening means of information travel. Second authentication for future estimation, analysis and reference, giving room for planner to multitask.

Process Optimization using Reactive AI-Driven tools	Description
Transparency in sharing information and Data integration	
Real-Time Updates And Centralized Information	Collaboration And Communication Enhanced Stakeholder Engagement And Transparency
Real-time Availability	AI-powered tools can provide real-time visibility into the availability of team members. Project managers can quickly identify and allocate resources based on their current workload and availability.
Cross-functional Team collaboration	AI-driven collaboration tools can improve team communication and coordination. Virtual project assistants can facilitate information sharing, task updates, and team collaboration.
Efficiency And Productivity	
Automated Task Management	AI-powered tools can automate repetitive and mundane tasks, allowing project managers to focus on more strategic aspects of project management.
Resource Scheduling, Shift Planning, Skill Matching	AI assists in employee shift planning by considering factors such as employee preferences, workload, and compliance with labor regulations. AI algorithms can distribute workloads more evenly among team members, preventing situations where some individuals are overloaded while others are underutilized. This helps maintain a balanced and efficient workforce. AI algorithms can analyze the skills and expertise of team members and match them with the requirements of specific project tasks. This ensures that resources with the right skill set are assigned to tasks, improving overall task performance.
Cost Optimization	AI can help optimize resource costs by identifying opportunities to use resources more efficiently. This includes minimizing overtime, reducing idle time, and avoiding unnecessary resource allocation.
Adaptive Scheduling	AI systems can adapt schedules dynamically based on changing project priorities, unexpected events, or delays. This flexibility ensures that resources are continuously optimized to meet project goals.
Reporting And Analytic For Informed Decision-Making:	
Data-Driven Decision Making:	AI analyzes various data points, including project timelines, resource availability, and historical performance, to provide data-driven insights for decision-making. Project managers can make informed choices regarding resource allocation, leading to better overall project outcomes. AI can assess project risks by analyzing various factors and historical data, providing insights into potential challenges. Early detection of risks allows project managers to implement mitigation strategies before issues escalate.
Learning and Improvement:	AI systems can learn from past resource allocation patterns and project outcomes, continuously improving their ability to make accurate predictions and recommendations. This iterative learning process enhances the effectiveness of resource scheduling over time.
Demand Forecasting:	AI can analyze historical project data and predict future resource requirements based on project scope, timelines, and complexity. This enables proactive resource planning, ensuring that the necessary skills and manpower are available when needed.
Decision Support Systems:	AI can assist project managers in making better decisions by analyzing complex data sets and providing recommendations. This helps in choosing the most optimal strategies and paths for project success. Project Forecasting: AI models can predict project outcomes based on historical data and current trends. This assists in setting realistic expectations and improving project planning.
Predictive Analytic:	AI algorithms can analyze historical project data to identify patterns and trends, enabling project managers to make more informed decisions. Predictive analytic can help forecast potential risks, resource requirements, and project timelines.

The Telegram Bot API interacts directly with Telegram to send and receive messages in natural language simple to understand from team members knowledge base, decision-making, action execution, response generation, output module (specifically tailored for Telegram), external systems integration, and feedback loop. The output module communicates with the Telegram Bot API to send responses back to users already pre-defined by the planner or team leader inputs. The feedback loop collects user feedback to improve the bots performance over time, which can be crucial for enhancing its effectiveness.

Flowchart Processes

Conclusion

With the advent of Generative AI in Project Management provides a competitive advantage even in the most demanding industries. Companies need to welcome change and prepare its workforce by investing in training on the use of AI tools and foster a culture of continuous learning. The benefits from the use case of reactive AI, which is the most basic form is easily deploy-able to automate mundane processes enhance productivity, capabilities and process improvement. The integration of this solution into project workflow is seamless by leveraging on a familiar environment.

Wolfgang Pauli